

'Our Maist Speciall Freindis': Using historical network analysis to study clan structures in early modern Scotland

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Prunte Katharina. 2024. "Our Maist Speciall Freindis': Using historical network analysis to study clan structures in early modern Scotland", *Historical Network Research* 2024, Lausanne, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12606001

This paper will explore the application of network analysis for examining clan structures and similar social systems during the early modern period. Drawing on examples from the Scottish *Gàidhealtachd*, a society historically viewed as backwards and simplistic due to their perceived failure to embrace opportunities for urbanisation and commercialisation, this paper demonstrates the use of HNA (historical network analysis) to study a seemingly unsophisticated social system and to trace soft power and influence outside formalised power structures.

Background

Throughout the medieval and early modern periods, Scotland was broadly divided into two distinct socio-linguistic spheres: the Scots-speaking Lowlands in the south and the east, and the Gaelic-speaking Highlands and Islands in the north and the west. While Lowlanders were generally perceived as civilised, law-abiding subjects to the Scottish Crown, the Gaelic clans inhabiting the western Highlands were instead regarded as a barbaric, savage people who refused to observe the law and lived only by the command of their warmongering chiefs. Studies by Alison Cathcart (2006), Aonghas MacCoinnich (2015), Martin MacGregor (2012) and others have done much to reform historians' perception of clan society, but one aspect that has yet to be addressed in detail is how clan chiefs governed their kindreds during this period and to what extent they could draw on processes of (in)formal consultation and representation inside the clan. Using HNR, this study will unpack social organisation and clan management in the western Highlands in the mid-sixteenth century to argue that the clans maintained a range of formal and informal socio-political structures of communication and representation which were crucial to foster their sense of shared identity and enable effective collective decision-making. The complexity of early modern clan communities has long been underestimated by historians but must be addressed to gain a better understanding of the Scottish *Gàidhealtachd*!

Research subject and approach

Traditionally, Scottish clans relied on a deeply personal system of rulership in which a chief provided for his kinsmen by dispensing resources, administering justice, and offering protection in return for loyalty and services rendered. Jane Dawson (2002) and Stephen Boardman (2006) have previously suggested that some Gaelic chiefs may have been aided in their duty to govern by a council or advisory board of their kinsmen, but the evidence available to historians using traditional research methods alone was never sufficient to prove the existence of any conciliar structures. Taking Dawson's suggestion of a 'clan council' within Clan Campbell in the sixteenth century as a starting point, this paper showcases how historians can combine historical network analysis with a close critical reading of land grants, precepts of sasine, witness lists, and bonds of manrent to prove the existence of two formal advisory bodies which had not previously been identified: an informal council, and a formal parliament or assembly of Campbell clansmen. Taken together, the council and assembly enabled effective communication and collective decision-making within the kindred, and allowed successive clan chiefs to draw on the expertise of their kinsmen and allies. Using a series of time snapshots of the networks underpinning Clan Campbell between 1558 and 1573, this paper further showcases how HNA may be used to trace the career and influence of individual councilmembers

and how we might distinguish between formal and informal conciliar structures within a clan, thereby offering novel insights into the organisation of Scottish clans during this period.

In this network, nodes are individual clansmen and places while edges are their direct ties based on letters, presence in the same location, or transactions/appointments. As such, if two individuals co-witness a charter or grant lands and offices to each other, they have a direct connection. Direct blood or foster relationships between members of a family are not coded as edges unless there was another transaction, direct communication, or other interaction to underpin the tie. Ties are undirected and not weighted. Clan communities usually had a small set of traditional names which were used with disproportionate frequency (e.g. John/Iain, Colin, Archibald, Donald etc) but, like many other early modern societies, did not follow any standardised spelling conventions while also switching between the Scottish and Gaelic version of the same name – as a consequence, John MacDonald might also be called Iain MacDonnell or indeed Iain, son of Donald/Dòmhnall, which makes identification difficult. To avoid artificial inflation of centrality scores, the dataset underpinning the networks treats two individuals with similar names as two separate nodes unless it can be demonstrated beyond reasonable doubt that they were the same person. The main sources for this dataset are the various charters and letters of Archibald Campbell, fifth earl of Argyll, and his kinsmen. The Argyll papers are an unusually rich source although they, like most family muniments or archives, are incomplete. So far, more than 1400 individuals and 150 places have been identified for the period between 1558 and 1573. Although places have also been coded as nodes, they are primarily used to identify whether individual persons had a particular connection to a geographic area and are otherwise excluded from the HNR part of the study since they cannot facilitate the flow of information and merely provide more context on the individual clansmen of Clan Campbell.

Research Questions

- 1) How can network analysis enable historians to study informal mechanisms of government in clan communities during the early modern period?
- 2) To what extent can network visualisations help identify individuals in formal and informal roles within a clan? How can HNA be used to distinguish between formal and informal advisors within a community?
- 3) Focussing on the example of Clan Campbell between 1558 and 1573, what evidence is there for the existence of one, or more, advisory boards that supported the clan chief in his duty to govern the wider kindred?

Wider implications

While this paper is concerned primarily with the identification of formal and informal conciliar structures within Scottish clans, there are wider implications for historical network analysis. Firstly, this study highlights that no society is too remote or too simplistic to be studied through network analysis. If HNA can reveal new insights into a society as ostensibly 'uncivilised' and unsophisticated as the Scottish *Gàidhealtachd*, there is no reason to believe that the same may not be true for other, similarly understudied communities. Secondly, the project highlights that network analysis does not always require a large volume of evidence to be applied successfully. Although many studies using HNA draw on extensive bodies of correspondence (e.g. the 'Republic of Letters' or the less well-known 'Tudor Networks'), a dearth of letters and similar documents does not automatically prevent historians from using network analysis. Most Gaels in the early modern period were unable to sign their names, let alone write a letter, but the surviving evidence from bonds, witness lists, and land grants can still be used to create and study a series of networks that offer fresh insights into their society. Finally, there can be no doubt that historical network analysis is well-suited to study social relationships, soft power, and influence outside formalised power structures. In some cases, as outlined above, HNA may indeed be able to detect otherwise imperceptible mechanisms of government and collaboration such as the existence of two separate conciliar structures which had previously gone unnoticed.

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